

Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science 2019-2020 Annual Report Summary

(SEE THE FULL REPORT [HERE](#))

General Information

The mission of AVDS is to increase **racial and ethnic equity** within the research programs at Oregon Health and Science University (OHSU) by recruiting, retaining, and most importantly supporting graduate students, postdoctoral scholars, staff, and faculty members from underrepresented backgrounds.

Main highlights from the year:

- We **restructured our group** (see image to right) from a classic hierarchical structure with a president at the top to a more decentralized power structure
- We formed 2 new committees, the **Policy Committee** and **Faculty Coalition**
- Huge growth, with a doubling in the number of committee members

We carry out our mission through **community building** and **policy change**. The achievements of our committees in these 2 areas is highlighted below.

AVDS new structure

Community Building

Education Committee Highlights

- Racial Justice Accomplice Training
- Quarterly documentary screenings
- AVDS Book Club
- Nonviolent Communication Training
- Host guest speaker Dr. Tirin Moore (*postponed due to COVID-19*)

AVDS newsletter subscribers by year

Events Committee Highlights

- Monthly Happy Hour
- Board Game Nights
- Graduate program recruitment

Communication Committee Highlights

- Growth in newsletter subscribers and visitors to our website
- Growth and streamlining of external communications

Policy Change

Operations Committee Highlights

- Coordinated establishment of AVDS Lounge
- Standardized surveys and internal data collection/analysis, started a GitHub repo that we will make open access
- Assessed School of Medicine Annual Diversity Report
- Aided with revision of SOM Diversity Action Plans

Board members & Policy Committee

- Helped publish and present (to the OHSU Board of Executives) a new model for [Revising OHSU's approach to racial diversity, equity, and inclusion](#)
- Chief Research Officer has committed to piloting our proposal of "REI" (Racial Equity & Inclusion) Centers

Faculty Coalition - Formed at the end of the year - stay tuned!

Use of Funding

a4vdis.weebly.com

a4vdis@ohsu.edu

@A4VDiS

@AVDS-PDX